

Effects of Plasticizations of Members on Seismic Response Reductions by Plural TMDs for Cylindrical Lattice Shell Roofs with Various Mass of Supporting Substructures

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Abstract

When TMDs (Tuned Mass Dampers) are applied to spatial structures, their seismic response reduction effect is influenced by the free vibration characteristics of the structure (Kumagai et al. [1]). However, when member yielding occurs, leading to an extension of the natural period, the response reduction effect can be predicted to decrease. Therefore, this study focuses on cylindrical lattice shell roofs with various half-open angles and substructure masses and analyzes the seismic response reduction effects by plural TMDs as the seismic intensity λ_E is gradually increased. The analysis is conducted from the perspectives of plastic rotation angles of members and absorbed energy by the TMDs, among other factors.

Keywords: Cylindrical lattice shell roof, Plural TMDs, Seismic response reduction effect, Dynamic elasto-plastic response analysis, Free vibration characteristic, Plastic rotation angle.

1. Introduction

TMD (Tuned Mass Damper) is fit for the vibration control of spatial structure because it is possible to install TMDs by a single supporting point. However, research on the optimal design of plural TMDs that simultaneously control multiple natural vibration modes remains limited (Kumagai et al. [2]). Additionally, there has been insufficient evaluation of the seismic response reduction performance of TMDs tailored to the shape and characteristics of spatial structures, particularly when structural members undergo plasticization under large seismic excitations. Therefore, this study investigates the seismic response reduction effect of plural TMDs applied to cylindrical lattice shell roofs with various half open angles and substructure masses, where the TMDs are designed based on the free vibration characteristics in the elastic state. First, the natural vibration modes to be controlled are selected. Next, a numerical analysis is conducted, in which the seismic intensity is gradually increased, to evaluate the plastic rotation angles of structural members and the absorbed energy by the TMDs, thereby analyzing the effect of natural period changes due to plasticization on the vibration control performance. Finally, an attempt is made to estimate the seismic response based on the energy absorption characteristics of the TMDs.

2. Analysis models and numerical analysis methods of cylindrical lattice shell roofs

2.1. Analysis models

The analysis models for this study are cylindrical lattice shell roofs with substructures as shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. The target structure is a cylindrical lattice shell roof. The boundary condition is fixed at the column bases, and the roof structure and substructure are fully pin-connected.

Figure 1: Analysis model (cylindrical lattice shell roof with substructure)

Table 1: Dimensions of shell roof

Half open angle	θ [deg.]	20	30	40
Span	L_x [m]	36		
Width	L_y [m]	48		
Radius of curvature	R [m]	53	36	28
Rise	H [m]	3.17	4.82	6.55
Height of Substructure	H_s [m]	4.0		
Total mass of shell structure	M_0 [t]	290	302	317

Table 2 lists the mass ratio R_M , which is defined by the following equation:

$$R_M = M_{eq} / M_R \quad (1)$$

Where M_{eq} is the equivalent mass of the single-degree-of-freedom model, M_R is the mass of the roof structure.

Based on the above variables, the model names are defined as follows:

Model Name: $F\theta$ (20, 30, 40) - R_M (Mass Ratio)

The mass ratio R_M is varied by multiplying the reference substructure effective mass M_S (61.7 t) by 1, 7.5, and 15. Table 3 provides the member properties and Figure 2 shows the thickness distribution of lattice members. All members in the model are assumed to be circular steel pipes.

Table 2: List of R_M

Half open angle θ [deg.]	Mass ratio of the substructure		
	1	7.5	15
20	1.3	2.7	4.9
30	1.3	2.7	4.9
40	1.2	2.6	4.7

Table 3: Member properties

	Half open angle φ [deg.]	Slenderness ratio λ	Diameter D [cm]	Thickness t [cm]	Sectional area A [cm ²]	Geometrical moment of inertia I [cm ⁴]
	Lattice member	20	18.0 ~ 35.9	31.85	0.35, 0.45, 0.65	34.6, 44.4, 63.7
30		21.4 ~ 42.9	26.74	0.35, 0.45, 0.60	29.0, 37.2, 49.3	2527, 3212, 4211
40		26.6 ~ 53.2	21.63	0.35, 0.45, 0.55	23.4, 29.9, 36.4	1325, 1680, 2025
Post	20	15.9 ~ 28.8	31.85	0.65	63.7	7756
	30	28.7 ~ 52.2	26.74	0.60	49.3	4211
	40	47.9 ~ 87.9	21.63	0.55	36.4	2025
Arch of gable direction		14.4	60.96	1.00	188.4	84677
Beam of gabel direction		27.5 ~ 28.7	60.96	0.75	141.9	64298
Beam of longitudinal		18.9	60.96	1.00	188.4	84677
Column		16.2	71.12	1.1	242.0	148329

Figure 2: Thickness distribution of lattice members

The Young's modulus E of the steel is set to 206,000 N/mm², and the specified design strength F is 235 N/mm². The bending stiffness of the roof structural members and the model where the mass ratio M_S is 1.0 is determined separately for the lattice members, boundary members (gable-end arches, gable-end beams, longitudinal beams, and struts), and substructure members (columns and beams in the gable and longitudinal directions). For the roof structure, the member cross-sections are determined based on the short-term allowable stress design with a safety factor $\nu=2.5$ according to the Allowable Stress Design Criteria for Steel Structures (et al. [3]). This ensures that the safety factor remains nearly uniform under dead loads.

For the model with a base substructure mass ratio of 1.0, a global buckling resistance verification is conducted according to literature [4], and the design ensures that the safety factor is 1.5 or higher under self-weight and a uniformly distributed snow load of 0.5 m. The substructure is designed to remain within the elastic range under shear forces and dead loads, assuming an A_i distribution with a base shear coefficient $C_0=0.3$.

The fundamental period ratio R_T , defined by the equation below, is calculated for each half open angle as follows:

$$R_T = T_{eq} / T_R \quad (2)$$

Where T_{eq} is the natural period of the equivalent single-degree-of-freedom model and T_R is the natural period of the antisymmetric first-wave mode of the roof structure model.

The calculated values of R_T are 0.401 for 20 degrees, 0.407 for 30 degrees, and 0.406 for 40 degrees.

Here, T_{eq} represents the natural period of the equivalent single-degree-of-freedom model, while T_R represents the natural period of the antisymmetric first-wave mode of the roof structure model.

The material properties of the members are assumed to follow a bi-linear model for the roof structure, whereas all other members are considered elastic as shown in Figure 3. The yield stress σ_y is 294N/mm².

Figure 3: Material Properties

The dead loads are set as follows: Roof structure: 1.18 kN/m², Substructure: 0.98 kN/m². The mass equivalent to the dead load is applied to each node as a lumped mass. In this paper, the node names shown in Figure 1 are used. Additionally, the line connecting nodes A, O, and A' is referred to as the central axis.

2.2. Numerical analysis Methods

The methods of analyses are a natural vibration analysis, a response spectrum analysis and a time history response analysis which takes into account the geometrical nonlinearity. The response spectrum analysis is conducted using the following equation:

$${}_k D_j^V = \left| {}_k \beta \cdot {}_k u_j^V \cdot {}_k S_D \right| \quad (3)$$

where ${}_k D_j^V$ is the maximum vertical response displacement, ${}_k \beta$ is participation factor, ${}_k u_j^V$ is vertical component of eigenvector, ${}_k S_D$ is the value of displacement response spectrum, the subscript k is the order of mode, the subscript j is the order of nodes, N_j is the number of nodes of the whole shell roof.

A numerical integration scheme for time history response analysis is the Newmark $\beta = 1/4$ method. The time increment Δt is 0.005sec. Rayleigh damping is applied to the damping of shell structure. The damping factor h is 2% for 1st and 2nd modes.

2.3. Input Seismic Waves

The input seismic waves are applied in the horizontal x-direction, as shown in Figure 1. The seismic waves used in this study consist of two types: a simulated seismic wave that retains the phase characteristics of the El Centro NS (1940) (hereafter referred to as the El Centro NS simulated wave) and a random phase wave (hereafter referred to as the random wave). The simulated seismic waves are generated based on the amplification coefficients specified for Type II ground in Notification No. 1461 of the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport, and Tourism, Japan, while also considering the surface ground amplification characteristics specified in MLIT Notification No. 1457.

The generated simulated seismic waves have maximum input accelerations A_g of 98.3 cm/s² and 104.8 cm/s² at $\lambda_E=1.0$. Since this study focuses on steel frame structures with a damping ratio of 2% for the first and second modes, the acceleration reduction rate due to damping is considered when generating the simulated seismic waves. Specifically, the acceleration response spectrum with a damping ratio of 5% is scaled by a factor of 1.25 to account for damping effects, and the modified simulated seismic waves are created accordingly. The corrected target acceleration response spectrum is presented in Table 4, while Figure 4 shows the acceleration response spectrum ($h = 2\%$) of the input seismic waves, where S_A represents the spectral acceleration values.

Table 4: Acceleration response spectrum used for the response spectrum analysis

Period T [s]	$T \leq 0.16$	$0.16 \leq T \leq 0.864$	$0.864 \leq T$
Acceleration response [cm/s ²]	$120 + 1125T$	300	$259 / T$

Figure 4: Acceleration response spectra of input earthquake motions

The input acceleration of the seismic waves is expressed in terms of seismic intensity λ_E . In accordance with Notification No. 1461, the damage limit level is defined as $\lambda_E=1.0$, while the safety limit level is defined as $\lambda_E=5.0$. In the analysis, the seismic intensity λ_E is gradually increased up to 18.0.

3. Selection of controlled modes

The controlled vibration modes, which are the vibration modes to be controlled using TMDs, are determined through natural vibration analysis and response spectrum analysis. Spatial structures inherently exhibit characteristics where multiple modes are dominant, and in some cases, these modes include higher-order modes. However, since the response displacement of higher-order modes is relatively small, it is difficult to effectively control them using TMDs.

Therefore, in this study, the selection of controlled modes follows the method proposed in the study (Kumagai *et al.* [1]), where response spectrum analysis is conducted using the acceleration response spectrum based on MLIT Notifications No. 1457 and 1461. The modes that contribute significantly to response displacement are selected as controlled modes.

The controlled modes for each model are presented in Table 5 and Figure 5. Table 5 includes the free vibration characteristics of the controlled modes, the ratio of maximum vertical response displacement κR_D^V at all nodes, and the total sum of the maximum response displacement ratios for all controlled modes. Additionally, the table provides the total sum of the maximum vertical response acceleration ratios κR_A^V .

Figure 5: Controlled modes

Name of model	F20 -R _c 1.3			F20 -R _c 2.7			F20 -R _c 4.9			F30 -R _c 1.3			F30 -R _c 2.7			F30 -R _c 4.9			F40 -R _c 1.2			F40 -R _c 2.6			F40 -R _c 4.7					
Modes	1st	6th		1st	6th	10th	1st	6th	10th	1st	6th	7th	1st	6th	7th	1st	6th	9th	1st	3rd	9th	2nd	3rd	9th	2nd	3rd	10th			
Number of antinodes of modes	2	2		2	2	6	2	2	6	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4
Natural period T [s]	0.826	0.335		0.798	0.337	0.286	0.773	0.339	0.286	0.866	0.385	0.325	0.810	0.379	0.338	0.769	0.377	0.343	0.892	0.549	0.340	0.822	0.536	0.351	0.780	0.526	0.355			
Effective mass ratios [%]	2.8	90.1		0.8	96.3	1.7	0.4	97.7	1.0	5.7	24.5	67.6	1.7	14.8	82.1	0.9	9.8	87.9	7.7	10.4	73.4	2.1	4.4	90.5	1.0	2.8	93.7			
Sum of effective mass ratios [%]	92.9			98.8			99.6			97.8			98.6			98.6			91.5			98.3			97.5					
Ratios of maximum vertical response acceleration $R_a R_d^v$ [%]	20.9	33.4		19.5	34.4	27.8	24.0	41.2	34.6	18.4	34.0	34.3	14.4	39.7	39.2	12.4	38.8	37.4	18.5	22.4	27.7	15.0	22.2	24.1	14.1	24.2	23.7			
Sum of ratios of maximum vertical response acceleration [%]	54.3			81.7			99.8			86.7			93.3			77.6			68.6			61.3			62.3					
Ratios of maximum vertical response displacement $R_d R_d^d$ [%]	66.0	17.4		62.2	19.6	11.4	65.5	21.5	12.9	59.2	21.6	15.5	47.1	28.3	22.3	40.7	30.7	24.5	54.2	24.9	11.8	46.5	29.3	13.7	41.7	32.6	14.5			
Sum of ratios of maximum vertical response displacement [%]	83.4			93.2			99.9			96.3			97.7			95.9			90.9			89.5			88.8					

Table 5: Free vibration characteristics of the controlled mode

4. Design and Installation of TMDs

The installation position of the TMDs is set on the roof surface, where they are placed at nodes corresponding to antinodes of the mode shape. Specifically, TMDs are installed at nodes where the vertical component of the mode shape vector is at least 80% of its maximum value, when the maximum value is normalized to 1.

For modes where two points satisfy this condition, a dual TMD (double TMD) system is applied. For four modes, a quadruple TMD system is used, and for six modes, a sextuple TMD system is employed. Figure 6 illustrates an example of the selected installation points for the F20-2.7 model. The TMDs are installed sequentially from node A to node A', starting with the TMD with the longest period.

The installation direction of the TMDs is set vertically downward, meaning that the TMDs oscillate in the vertical (z) direction.

Figure 6: Installation of TMDs

Next, the calculation methods for the tuning ratio and damping ratio of each TMD are explained. In this study, dual TMDs, quadruple TMDs, and sextuple TMDs are considered, and each system is designed using different optimal condition equations. Eqs.(4) ~ (6) define the mass ratio, tuning ratio, and damping ratio of the TMDs.

$$\mu_N = \frac{m_T}{kM_j} \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma_N^{(n)} = \frac{\omega_0}{\omega_T^{(n)}} = \frac{T_T^{(n)}}{T_0} \quad (5)$$

$$\zeta_N^{(n)} = \frac{c_T T_T^{(n)}}{4m_T \pi} \quad (6)$$

Where n is the order in which the periods of TMDs are long, N is the number of installing TMD, m_T is the mass of one TMD, kM_j is the equivalent mass of i th mode, T_T is the period of TMD, T_0 is the natural period of controlled mode and c_T is the damping factor of TMD.

5. Influence of seismic intensity on the response reduction efficiency of plural TMDs

The relationship between seismic intensity λ_E and the reduction rate $Re_{A_v}^{shell}$ (Eq. (7)), which is the square root of the sum of squared vertical response accelerations at all nodes over all analysis steps, is shown in Figure 7.

$$Re_{A_v}^{shell} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} (A_{Vij}^{shell-c})^2}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} (A_{Vij}^{shell-unc})^2}} \quad (7)$$

Where the subscript c represents the controlled condition, while unc represents the uncontrolled condition. N_j denotes the total number of nodes in the structure, and N_i represents the total number of analysis steps.

Figure 7: Relationship between seismic intensity and reduction rates of vertical response accelerations

In F30 and F40, the reduction rate gradually deteriorates when the seismic intensity λ_E exceeds the initial yielding intensity λ_{Ey} . In this study, the plastic rotation angle θ_{pl} is adopted as a quantitative index for plasticization. Figure 8 shows the relationships between λ_E and the total plastic rotation angles θ_{pl} of lattice members. Regardless of the model, the installation of TMDs effectively reduces plastic rotation angles. Figure 9 presents the distribution of the maximum vertical response ratio along AOA' for $\lambda_E = 1.0, 10, 14$ and 18 under both uncontrolled and controlled conditions. As λ_E increases, the response reduction effect diminishes. In terms of displacement response ratio, at $\lambda_E = 18$, certain nodes exhibit a higher response in the controlled condition than in the uncontrolled condition.

Figure 8: Relationships with seismic intensity (Random wave input, Member rotation angle)

Figure 9: Maximum vertical response acceleration magnification factors (Line AOA', Random wave, F40-RM1.2)

Figure 10 displays the natural vibration characteristics and controlled modes corresponding to the target period of the TMDs at $\lambda_E = 10$ and $\lambda_E = 18$, when the maximum vertical response displacement occurs. The mode shapes corresponding to the controlled TMD periods are also illustrated. At $\lambda_E = 10$, which is close to λ_{Ey} , there is no significant change in the controlled modes (1st, 3rd, and 9th modes). However, at $\lambda_E = 18$, the vibrational characteristics within the target control period have altered, leading to a deterioration in the response reduction effect as λ_E increases.

Figure 10: Natural vibration characteristics and target control period modes during elasto-plastic response (F40- R_M 1.2, Random Wave input, at Maximum vertical response displacement)

6. Response reduction effect evaluated based on energy absorption by TMDs

Figure 11 illustrates the relationship between seismic intensity λ_E and the difference in the total plastic rotation angle $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ between the uncontrolled and controlled cases. As λ_E increases beyond the initial yielding seismic intensity λ_{Ey} , the difference in $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ grows rapidly. In F30 and F40, regardless of the mass ratio R_M , the difference in $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ initially increases and then gradually decreases. This suggests that for λ_E up to approximately 10, $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ continues to increase, indicating an effective suppression of member plasticization. Figure 12 presents the relationship between the energy absorption rate of the TMDs, E_{TMD}/E_S^{unc} , and the reduction rate Re_{AV}^{shell} for each λ_E . Here, E_S^{unc} represents the total input energy of the shell structure in the uncontrolled case, while E_S^{unc} and E_{TMD} denote the total input energies of the shell structure alone and the TMDs alone in the controlled case, respectively. When E_{TMD}/E_S^{unc} and Re_{AV}^{shell} correspond, the data points align with the dotted line in the figure. Regardless of whether plasticization occurs in the members, E_{TMD}/E_S^{unc} decreases as λ_E increases. In F30 and F40, once E_{TMD}/E_S^{unc} decreases to approximately 0.1, Re_{AV}^{shell} deteriorates. In contrast, for F20, where $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ remains small, the variation of E_{TMD}/E_S^{unc} with λ_E is minimal.

Figure 11: Relationships between E_{TMD} and $E_S^{unc} - E_S^c$

Figure 12: Relationships between TMD energy absorption ratio and vertical response reduction ratio

7. Conclusions

It is concluded as follows, from the above results.

- 1) The reduction rate of vertical response acceleration deteriorates at seismic intensity levels λ_E beyond the initial yielding seismic intensity λ_{Ey} .
- 2) As λ_E increases beyond λ_{Ey} , the natural vibration characteristics at the controlled target period of the TMDs change.
- 3) For λ_E up to approximately 10, the difference in the total plastic rotation angle $\sum \theta_{pl}$ between the uncontrolled and controlled cases increases, indicating an effective suppression of member plasticization.
- 4) Regardless of whether plasticization occurs in the members, the energy absorption rate of the TMDs decreases with increasing λ_E , and in the analysis models with half open angles of 30 and 40deg., once it decreases to approximately 0.1, the reduction rate of the root mean square acceleration deteriorates.

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